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CORPORATE FINANCE IN RUSSIA

This article explores the essence of corporate finance, its institutional composition, and characterizes financial and non-financial corporations. An analysis of financial indicators is used to characterize their place and role in the Russian economy.

Using analytical and synthesis methods, this article formulates the essence of corporate finance and presents the institutional structure and organizational and legal composition of the Russian corporate sector. Using analytical research methods, we identified the dominant position of the corporate sector in the national economy, the predominance of non-financial corporations in creating added value and generating profit and loss for the corporate sector, and substantiated the dominance of financial corporations in accumulating financial assets. A graphical approach allows us to clearly demonstrate the results and conclusions of the research presented in this article.

The article also draws conclusions regarding the reasons for the dominance of the limited liability company among corporate organizational and legal forms.

The regional aspect of the study is reflected in the study of the corporate sector of the Donetsk People's Republic.

Keywords: corporate finance, corporate sector, institutional structure, financial corporations, non-financial corporations, gross value added, gross profit, profitability, corporate sector liabilities.

...

[1].

2020 2610063 2020-2021 .(5,0%),

2024 3436556 [12] 2022-2024 . 0,03 %.

2023- 2024 , 04.10.2022 N 5- « » [7].

— 29,63 %.

1

.I.

2020-2024 ., .([9])

01.01.2021 . 3436556

, 2788583

2610063 . 2597028 ., (.1).

2024 99,50 % , 2020 81,14 %,

54,67 % 2023 88,44 % 2024 .

114

I. 2020-2024 . . *

\		2020	2021	2022	2023	2024	, %
1.	-	3 436 556	3 274 285	2 609 108	2 610 063	2 610 063	75,95
2.	-	2 788 583	2 636 997	2 578 576	2 580 105	2 597 028	93,13
	:						
2.1	-	2727921	2579867	2525515	2528124	2544116	93,26
2.2		60310	56823	52331	51721	52671	87,33
2.3		352	307	730	260	241	68,47

* [9]

2788583 . 2020 2597028 . 2024 , 93,13 %.

—97,82

% 2020 97,96 % 2024 . , ,

(12,76 % 6,74 %).

2 - (.3)

2. 2020-2024 . ([9])

. 3.

2023-2024 . ([9])

—0,27% 0,2% 98,72% 98,96%, —1,01% 0,84%.,
2023 2024 .

2020 2023

24,0% 2013 4,01% 2023 . [1],

[4]

2020-2024 .
209,44%.

271,94% 205,62%

(.4)

[4]

116

4. 2020-2024 ., % ([4])

«...
/ ,
» [5].
2024

(.2).

2.

, 2020-2024 ., % *

\		2020	2021	2022	2023
1	, %	100,0	100,0	100,0	100,0
2	, %	76,78	75,81	79,07	81,05

* [4]

2

70,0%

2020 2023

70%,

6. 2020-2024 ([10])

3. 2020-2024 .. . *

/		2020	2021	2022	2023	2024	, %
1	,	39 445	57 680	75 341	101363,6	96128,65	243,7
1.1		12 506	27 190	24 936	43608,7	43054,76	344,26
1.2		14 462	14 796	32 947	33088,52	27766,84	192,0

* [13]

2030 «...

»[11].

239,42 % , 88909,31 2024 , 2020 .

7.

. 7.

2020-2024 ., . . ([13])

2023 .

2024 .

(. 8).

110,35 %,

. 8.

2020-2024 ., % ([4, 13])

120

2024 . 321,04 %, . 2020 .

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